

COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION IN RURAL WATER SUPPLY IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Majority of rural Nigerian households do not have access to improved water supply despite several policies and programmes by successive administrations. This study is an attempt to assess the level of community participation in rural water supply in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The research focused on the rural participation approaches, and the influence of socio-economic factors of rural dwellers in rural water supply. The study adopted combination of survey and cross – sectional research methods in the collection of data in the study area. Ninety – three rural communities were randomly selected using the quadrat sampling technique. The questionnaire was statistically administered to four targeted population: the household – heads, village heads, Local Government Council Officials and Community-Based Organizations (CBOs) on issues bordering on participation in rural water supply projects in the study area. Tables and percentages were used to analysed data at univariate level while multiple regression and factor analysis were used for the testing of the two research hypotheses at the bivariate levels. The result of the study showed that technical assistance factor (X3) contributed the highest in predicting the approaches of rural participation with (0.961) factor score loading while labour interaction factor (X8) contributed the least (0.484) factor score loading in the explanation of the rural participation approaches in rural water supply in the study area. On the socio-economic influence; formally educated and married youth factor (X2) contributed the highest factor of (0. 531) while religious income factor (X6) contributed the least factor (0.450) in the explanation of the socio -economic factors influencing rural water supply in the study area. The study, therefore, recommends that the social-economic status of the people should be alleviated by enforcing compulsory education at the junior secondary level and encouraging entrepreneurial skills acquisition among the youths. This would make them to effectively participate in rural water projects and also the labour interaction approach should be strengthened to ensure effective participation in rural of rural water projects.

Keywords: *Community Participation, Rural Water, Sustainability, Rural Dwellers, Nigeria.*

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1. Introduction

Global population increase continues to create new and more challenges to the problem of clean and potable water supply both in rural and urban areas. Studies by Chitonge (2014), Hopewell and Graham (2014) and Gleick (2014) show that the challenges will be more phenomenal in emerging cities in Africa where these facilities are urgently needed. The daunting task facing local authorities is how to adequately supply clean potable water to the predominantly poor rural dwellers (Bakker *et al.*, 2008). Experts and practitioners in the development studies have proposed varied management models targeted at improving access to water supply in the developing world (Ghai and Vivian 2014; Wraight, 2008, Mitchel, 2005; World Bank, 2004 and Gleick, 2003).

Reports has established that billions of people worldwide are living without access to safe water with the vast majority of these people living in the rural communities (UNICEF and WHO, 2019). Poor quality of water has been implicated in 80% of all sickness and diseases worldwide through inadequate sanitation, polluted water, or unavailability of potable water supply (WHO, 2019), and at any given moment it has been estimated that half the world's hospital beds are occupied with patients suffering from water-related diseases (UNICEF, 2021). One of the United Nation's 2000 Millennium Goals (MDG's) was to increase the proportion of the world's population that has access to safe drinking water and basic sanitation (United Nations, 2010). While the international community has made advancements toward this goal over the past decade, progress in rural areas is still lagging relative to urban areas (United Nations, 2011). Worldwide, 80 per cent of the people who have limited access to drinking water supplies live in rural areas (United Nations, 2010) The World Bank (2016) recognised the lack of community participation as a reason for the failure of many community development attempts in developing countries. Thus, it should be noted that community participation often means the involvement of 'the members of the community taking part in shaping, planning, developing, implementing and evaluating policies and actions which affect their lives and the life of their community. It has been established over the years that in water supply projects best results are obtained only when communities are involved in the planning and running of the project (Joseph, 2015, Koffi and Ikurekong 2020 and Ananga *et al.*, 2020).

Over the years successive governments in Nigeria have introduced various programmes to arrest problems militating against the development of rural Nigeria such as Operation Feed the

Nation (OFN), Directorate of Food, Roads, and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI) Programme, Farm Settlement Scheme of the then Western Region, River Basin Development Authorities (RBDA) projects, and Integrated Rural Development (IRD) projects among others (Simon *et.al.*, 2014). All these programmes have failed to contribute effectively to the development of rural communities especially the introduction and implementation of hand pumps water supply projects by DFRRI to various rural locations in South-Eastern Nigeria. One major factor has been identified as the failure of these programmes; which is the lack of effective community participation of rural dwellers at various stages in water project execution (Brain and Robert 2016 and Muniu *et al.*, 2017).

Research has also proved that lack of community participation has been a reason for the failure of many development projects in developing countries across the globe (World Bank, 2016). This is the foundation of the problem of this research which concerns the lack of effective participation of rural dwellers in water projects in Akwa Ibom State. This may be attributed to the challenge of identifying and implementing the various approaches of rural participation in water supply projects. However, most development project donors identify community participation as one of the prerequisites for improved performance in the water sector. It soon turned out that sustainable water supply services could not be achieved without involving the community not just in manual work, but also in the planning of programmes from the conceptualization stage to the final implementation stage (Therkildsen, 1998).

Although, researchers have conducted studies on community participation approach in social services delivery (Felix, 2004; Elizabeth, 2008; Williams, 2008), none of these studies attempted to provide empirical evidence related to the sustainability of water supply under community participation as an alternative approach of providing water supply in the study area. Apparently, the absence of effective participation in rural water projects in the study area resulted in many projects uncertainty in sustainability, they function for short periods and collapse after funding institutions cease to provide support both financially and technically (Acha. J 2020). This has resulted in a decline in the water consumption level of the rural populace from the standards required. Therefore, this study seeks to fill the research gap by identifying an approach or combination of approaches that ensures effective rural participation for sustainable rural water supply in rural Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Empirical Review

Scholars and development practitioners have established a typology of participation approaches where the level of participation is assessed on the involvement of community in the development projects. Among the scholars is Arnstein (1969) who postulated eight (8) rungs on the level of citizen participation and categorized it into three categories. The top of the ladder according to Arnstein is a symbol of full or genuine participation, the two bottom rungs of ladder represent non-participation; where people are allowed to participate, but it does not give them any opportunity to change programmes to their own needs and as a result maintains their status quo.

The third category of participation encompasses the degree of tokenism, which allows the participation to be heard, to have a voice. Thus, citizen gains some degree of influence though it is still a form of tokenism as traditional power-holders continue to have the right to decide. It is the illusion of a voice without the voice itself. However, studies by Taylor *et al.*, (2008) Cited in Preston *et al.*, (2010) outlined four conceptual approaches to community participation which were; contribution approach, instrumental, empowerment and developmental approach and diagnosis how each of these approaches were applied in community water supply projects. Essentially, community participation promotes greater chances of success for development initiatives, efficiency in the use of resources, effectiveness, self-reliance, empowerment, sustainability and ownership of development initiatives (Botes, 2013; Davids, *et al.*, 2009 Kumar, 2002; Brehanu, 2008). Nwankwoala (2011) reveals that there is no doubt that efficient and sustainable water resources management in Nigeria requires the participation of local communities. In addition, Njoh (2003) contends that participation had long been practiced by the indigenous communities before the arrival of the Europeans. Specifically, in a book titled Self - help water supply in Cameroon, Njoh stated that in pre-colonial Africa, it was common for communities to join hands in local development projects. Such projects included building chiefs' palaces, market centers, erecting village bridges, or building community centers (Ananga *et. al* 2020).

Moreso, review of literatures agrees that socio-economic factors have influence on community participation in rural water supply in both developed and developing countries. For instance, Bauma *et al.*, (2000) argue that the level of participation is significantly influenced by individual socio-economic status and other demographic characteristics. According to Jones (2011), a study conducted on community participation in water supply in Mali revealed that citizenship were

affected by four key structural factors namely age, level of education, gender and geographic location. The studies of Hassan *et al.*, (2019), Gaboyan (2010), Harris (2006) and Toner and Clever, (2006) all agrees that age has a significant influenced on rural people participation in rural water supply project. Young and active age bracket between 18 – 55 years tends to participate more than the old people from 60 years and above. Nevertheless, John, (2009) opined that educational level of the citizenry has a significant correlation in the level of participation in rural water supply. Similarly, Joshi and Houtzager (2012) contends that education has a high positive correlation with publics engagement in rural water supply, while Mugizi *et al.*, (2017) argued that education is essential in enhancing long-term participation of local community in any development initiatives. The level of education in the community affects the level of community participation in water projects (Dorsner 2004). Speer *et al.*, (2013 and Shamiyulla and Ramu (2010) established in their separate findings that the level of education is a significant variable influencing community participation in rural water supply in rural communities. Lack of adequate knowledge and skills by the community members due to the high level of illiteracy have limited the scope of community participation in rural water development and thus perpetuating continues lack of safe and clean water within many communities.

However, the study of Awortwi (2012) in Africa and Latin America concluded that income levels have positive relationships as a factor influencing community participation in rural water supply. In rural Kenya, it was established that the weak financial position of local communities not only reduces their capacity to participate in development projects, but also affect their ability to pay for water services (Kakumba and Nsingo, 2008). In addition, Phillip and Abdillahi (2003) report agrees with Awortwi (2012) findings that the relatively high level of participation depends on the household income earned per month. Therefore, a decrease in household income per month is associated with a decrease in the level of community participation in rural water projects in terms of monetary contribution. Similarly, findings of Ezenwaji *et al.*, 2016 on factors influencing community participation in rural water projects in Matete Sub-County Kakamega County revealed that the low-income of the community affected their ability to give monetary contribution towards planning and implementation of community water projects in the study area. The community members who have high income levels were able to contribute towards water project implementation than those with lower income level. From Gender Perspective, Hassan *et al.*, (2019) established that men tend to show greater participation in water development activities than

their female counterparts. Gender has been widely noted as an important factor influencing participation, particularly in rural water supply projects (Cleaver, 2002; Cleaver and Toner, 2006; Singh, 2008; Sultana, 2009).

3. METHODOLOGY

Geographically Akwa Ibom State is located in the coastal south-southern part of the country, lying between Latitude 4° 32' and 5° 31.1' North of Equator, and Longitudes 7° 25' and 8° 25' East. It has inter-state boundaries with Cross River to the east, Abia to the north and north-west and Rivers to the southwest and to the south is the Gulf of Guinea. The study adopted a combination of survey and cross-sectional methods because it allows the researcher to collect data from different groups of people/individuals at a particular point in time. The survey approach was used to collect data through questionnaires on four different targeted populations that made up the study area Akwa Ibom State. Primarily, data requirements for the study were sourced through the use of pre-tested structured questionnaires, and personal observations on existing water supply projects in the study area while books, journals, and relevant reports/publications on the subject matter were consulted to beef up the secondary method of data collection. The population data of rural dwellers in the state was extracted from the 1991 National Population Census figure. The population figure for each of the settlements in the state was projected to the year 2024, using a 2.83 percent population growth rate. However, the selection of rural household heads from the sample communities was facilitated by drawing a map of Akwa Ibom State on a scale of 1cm to represent 1km, and dividing it into quadrats of 0.025km² which were clearly and serially numbered. The quadrat system allows for random selection of a required number of points or cases within a quadrat. A table of random numbers was used to select rural communities as units of observation from sampled quadrats because the grid maps contain the names of communities thus, it was easy to know the communities within each quadrat.

In the context of this research, where a quadrat contained two or more communities, only one with the highest population was selected to represent such quadrat. However, where a quadrat contained a community with a population of 20,000 and above, such quadrat was skipped considering the rural focus of the study. The study adopted a 10% sample fraction and a total of 93 out of 930 quadrats from a preliminary analysis was randomly selected using the table of random numbers. To determine the sample size for rural household heads in the sample communities,

the researcher adopts Stroud and Booth (2007) formula in determining the sample size which is stated below;

$$S = \frac{N - P(N)}{n}$$

where S = Required sample, P = Expected value at 70% base (Constant)

N = The total working population size, n = Number of working area (villages)

$$S = \frac{[(358433) - (0.7 \times 358433)]}{93}$$

$$S = \frac{107530}{93} = 1156$$

This implies that 1156 rural household-heads was selected from 93 settlements for water supply and community participation survey in Akwa Ibom State as shown in Table 1.

Sample Size: Table 1

S/N	Assigned no	Names of Villages	LGA	Population (2024)	Household Pop.	Sample Size
1	457	Ikot Akpaya	Etinan	3594	599	12
2	639	Ikot Umiang Ede	Etinan	3539	590	12
3	701	Akpasak Efa	Etinan	5849	975	17
4	550	Ikot Ananga	Etinan	2390	398	8
5	215	Atan Aya	Ibiono	1928	321	7
6	242	Afaha Nsai	Ibiono	3388	565	12
7	168	Ikot Idem	Ibiono	2470	412	9
8	266	Ikot Ada Idem	Ibiono	5816	969	17
9	933	Usuk Aka	Ibono	3497	583	12
10	244	Odiok Itam	Itu	4125	688	14
11	198	Ikot Antuen	Itu	3006	501	10
12	199	Ikot Offiong	Itu	6033	1006	17
13	114	Ndiya Etuk	Ikono	3665	611	12
14	092	Itak Ikot Akpan Edem	Ikono	3057	510	11
15	117	Ikot Onwong	Ikono	2404	400	8
16	163	Ekpen Obom Nkuoro	Ikono	2464	410	8
17	138	Ikot Ette	Ikono	1855	309	7
18	061	Etok Iton	Ikono	1571	262	7
19	210	Utu Edem Usuk	Ikot Ekpene	7679	1280	20
20	049	Ndot Nkpe	Ini	4242	707	14
21	048	Ibam Edet	Ini	3297	550	11

(table continues)

						Original Article	
22	195	Ikot Ukap	Itu	2677	446	9	
23	032	Edem Idim	Ini	2097	350	7	
24	645	Idikpa Nsit	Nsit Atai	2604	434	9	
25	558	Ikot Uyo	Nsit Atai	2281	380	8	
26	709	Ikot Okpudo	Nsit Ubium	4230	705	14	
27	516	Minya Ntak	Mkpat Enin	6397	1066	18	
28	586	Minya	Mkpat Enin	4622	770	15	
29	763	Ikot Etefia	Mkpat Enin	3268	545	11	
30	461	Ikot Annung	Ibesikpo	2659	443	9	
			Asutan				
31	431	Ikot Obio Odongo	Ibesikpo	5214	869	16	
			Asutan				
32	285	Ikot Akpasia	Ibesikpo	2379	397	8	
			Asutan				
33	583	Ekpene Ukpa	Etinan	9034	1506	25	
34	868	Odio	Eket	4738	790	15	
35	835	Esit Urua	Eket	7795	1299	21	
36	768	Ikot Abia	Eket	6147	1025	17	
37	870	Nditia	Eket	1819	303	7	
38	285	Afaha Esang	Abak	5871	979	17	
39	264	Ikot Obioko	Abak	3796	633	13	
40	314	Ikwek	Abak	3801	634	13	
41	341	Ikot Akpa Edem	Abak	2692	448	9	
42	443	Ikot Udo-Obong	Etim Ekpo	5158	860	16	
43	359	Nto Obio	Etim Ekpo	6020	1003	17	
44	360	Ikot Akpapan	Etim Ekop	2466	411	9	
45	474	Ndot	Etim Ekpo	2246	374	8	
46	237	Ikot Abiat	Essien Udium	2990	498	10	
47	205	Nto Nsek	Essien Udim	5793	966	16	
48	261	Ikot Akpan Essang	Essien Udim	2848	475	10	
49	236	Ikot Ntuen	Essien Udim	2661	444	9	
50	228	Iboho	Essien Udim	2286	381	8	
51	284	Mkpatak	Essien Udim	2150	358	8	
52	831	Abat	Onna	5098	850	16	
53	117	Ikot Onwon	Onna	5720	953	16	
54	224	Ikot Nya	Itu	1972	329	7	
55	678	Urue Ita	Okobo	4882	814	16	
56	468	Esuk Inwang Ekeya	Okobo	4167	695	14	
57	563	Ebighi Anwa	Okobo	3350	558	11	
58	562	Eyo Nko	Okobo	2615	436	9	
59	564	Nda	Okobo	1951	325	7	
60	010	Obot Ndom	Ini	2519	420	9	
61	109	Ikot Abia	Obot Akara	2861	477	10	
62	749	Uda	Mbo	5596	933	16	
63	717	Asak Ikang	Mbo	3701	617	13	
64	813	Iyesin	Mbo	2652	442	9	
65	847	Ibete	Mbo	2923	487	10	
66	384	Ikot Inyang	Ika	4076	679	14	
67	903	Mkpanak	Ibeno	16318	2720	48	
68	567	Esuk Mbiam	Oron	2288	381	8	
69	605	Mbiaso	Oruk Anam	2655	443	9	
70	756	Ikot Inuen	Oruk Anam	4381	730	15	
71	940	Obianga	Eastern Obolo	2377	396	8	
72	483	Ntak Ibesit	Oruk Anam	3252	542	11	

					Original Article	
73	759	Ikot Osudu	Ikot Abasi	2468	411	9
74	791	Ikot Akpa Idiayang	Ikot Abasi	2868	478	10
75	827	Atan Obom	Ikot Abasi	3083	514	11
76	792	Ikot Ukpong Ekwere	Ikot Abasi	3590	598	12
77	063	Atan Ukwuk	Ini	2008	335	7
78	327	Akani Obio Uruan	Uruan	4130	688	14
79	478	Ikot Akpaidem	Ukanafun	5764	961	16
80	510	Afaha Obo	Ukanafun	4282	714	14
81	713	Ubodung	Urue Offong	3992	665	14
82	684	Eyo Eyekip	Urue Offong	1888	315	7
83	692	Offot	Oruk Anam	2879	480	10
84	686	Eyo Nsek	Udung Uko	2599	433	9
85	773	Ekpene Obo	Esit Eket	11547	1925	33
86	742	Uquo Iso Edoho	Esit Eket	4412	735	15
87	838	Ine Ukpana	Esit Eket	4036	673	14
88	810	Ntak Inyang	Esit Eket	4036	673	14
89	806	Akpata	Esit Eket	2815	469	10
90	393	Ibesit Okpokoro	Oruk Anam	4296	716	15
91	610	Itung	Oruk Anam	2102	350	8
92	609	Eteben	Oruk Anam	2386	398	8
93	482	Ntak Obio Akpa	Oruk Anam	3783	631	13
				358433	59739	1156

Source: NPC, 1991.

The second target population was the total number of community leaders/village heads of the sample rural settlements in the study area. Questionnaire was administered to the selected 93 community leaders on their level of participation in water supply in the area. The third group was the number of Local Government Council Officials in- charge of community development projects. Finally, the fourth was the number of Community-Based Organizations (CBOs) in the rural settlements that make up the study area.

3.1 Data Presentation and Analysis

Two research approaches were presented and analysed on community participation in rural water supply in the study area. However, hypotheses one state that the rural participation approaches do not significantly influence the rural water supply options in the study area. To analysed this hypothesis, factor analysis was used to reduce 17 independent (x) variables of participation approaches into nine (9) extracted components with their factor score as shown in Table 2. while dependent variable (y) is water supply option.

Table 2: Extracted nine (9) components factor on rural participation of approach

Communities	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Ikot Akpaya	-1.07176	-1.65873	0.5956	-0.40933	0.8528	0.77963	0.82712	0.54251	-0.37109
Ikot Umiang									
Ede	-0.87901	1.20774	0.20948	-0.06873	-1.47503	1.38053	0.81058	-1.39974	-0.83946
Akpasak Efa	-0.95181	-1.00595	1.01702	0.0289	0.39688	-0.51639	1.0167	0.95485	-0.04103
Ikot Ananga	-0.93701	-0.59636	-1.72584	-0.46908	-0.77029	0.58143	0.8133	1.15685	-0.68889
Atan Aya	-0.77867	-0.10188	-1.35131	-0.68437	-0.68525	0.81674	0.40941	-1.47063	-0.67833
Afaha Nsai	-0.61575	1.78969	0.49778	-0.98921	-0.17269	0.3312	-0.06293	-0.11252	-0.62307
Ikot Idem	-0.12153	2.01349	0.27129	1.37838	-0.15882	0.04077	-0.69113	-0.69929	-1.06321
Ikot Ada Idem	-0.35407	-0.6841	0.78202	1.84476	0.45643	0.4279	-0.10448	1.40941	-0.39425
Usuk Aka	-0.76548	1.33891	-0.00428	-1.11804	-0.28473	-0.1457	0.15521	3.00645	-0.83842
Odiok Itam	1.09714	1.60208	0.20214	0.19348	-0.27299	1.01608	0.54667	-1.20936	-0.52394
Ikot Antuen	-0.30576	-0.88758	0.70943	0.10868	-0.04919	1.30899	-2.07171	-1.4551	-0.56714
Ikot Offiong	1.0237	1.36904	0.59879	0.13253	1.24597	0.10143	0.37295	-0.61299	2.70511
Ndiya Etuk	-0.98267	-1.41738	0.61798	-0.27388	0.19984	0.82324	0.85305	0.69942	-0.33915
Itak Ikot Akpan									
Edem	-0.27065	-0.57173	0.62909	2.26271	-1.05861	-1.17487	0.38333	-0.8585	-0.4433
Ikot Onwong	-0.60221	1.57179	0.20221	-0.95528	-0.33855	-2.12272	0.30035	0.84166	-0.47885
Ekpen Obom									
Nkuoro	-0.25471	0.09478	-1.51081	1.47336	-0.00598	-1.94712	-0.09968	-0.20435	-0.60536
Ikot Ette	-0.71525	-0.59835	0.61342	-1.32365	-0.43759	0.38936	-0.03942	-0.51598	-0.91743
Etok Iton	-0.87108	-0.97878	0.50752	-0.98355	-0.54617	0.80784	0.31792	-1.21897	-0.98664
Utu Edem									
Usuk	1.16961	1.65153	0.54103	0.94797	-0.27095	-0.80152	1.17427	-0.42336	0.44646
Ndot Nkpe	-0.35481	-1.11992	0.66731	0.2901	0.48228	0.92678	-1.86391	1.40468	-0.19042
Ibam Edet	-0.83226	-1.00379	0.63732	-0.50307	-0.6755	-1.17263	0.85487	-0.16685	-0.30296
Ikot Ukap	1.19638	1.56056	-0.0594	-0.22921	0.08222	-1.91492	0.53894	0.28051	-0.3991
Edem Idim	-0.70597	-0.81638	0.6259	-1.05362	0.00885	-1.87173	0.39	0.19288	-0.37321
Idikpa Nsit	-0.66258	1.67445	0.21271	-1.33374	-0.34402	0.11805	-0.16954	0.1692	-1.0075
Ikot Uyo	-0.33016	-1.1375	0.34803	0.26835	-0.30755	0.79324	-1.81632	1.18539	-0.56222
Ikot Okpudo	-0.7694	-0.17065	-1.07318	-0.95875	0.8174	-1.67845	0.43942	0.41967	0.08021
Minya Ntak	-0.67817	1.8514	0.5162	-1.30504	-0.22138	0.41962	-0.18428	0.98227	-0.68523

Table 2. cont: Extracted nine (9) components factor on rural participation of approaches

Ikot Etena	-0.29016	1.56025	0.24154	2.05294	0.77071	-0.00541	-0.11466	0.82209	-0.56758
Ikot Annung	-0.85246	-1.01372	0.83486	-1.18758	1.05114	0.5273	0.0581	-1.33083	-0.60332
Ikot Obio									
Odongo	-0.72268	-0.73673	1.13705	-0.02516	-0.30839	-0.92563	0.94106	-0.47372	0.3524
Ikot Akpasia	-0.30987	-0.05924	-1.50102	1.98475	-0.39971	-1.52476	0.26174	-0.95328	-0.51693
Ekpene Ukpa	-0.55137	-1.01072	1.01797	3.10698	-0.37716	1.78193	0.8098	0.25827	0.03874
Odio	-0.40649	-0.84232	0.64542	2.07446	0.04719	0.62066	0.11395	0.93267	-0.51704
Esit Urua	-0.34044	1.41682	0.68793	2.79652	0.59104	0.83109	0.3067	0.63571	0.03232
Ikot Abia	-0.55165	-0.37775	-1.56309	1.87803	-0.02824	0.70426	0.18595	1.40826	-0.71233
Nditia	-0.6271	-0.67445	0.79315	-0.60874	-0.28926	-1.67655	0.56387	-0.32894	-0.10851
Afaha Esang	-1.07731	-0.58227	-1.13186	-0.49206	-0.28412	0.70305	0.6706	-0.35936	2.32253
Ikot Obioko	-0.48016	-0.72462	0.4901	1.30886	-0.83136	0.04529	-0.34413	0.17498	1.502
Ikwek	-0.87659	1.13132	0.43991	-0.5734	0.34724	0.88539	0.39552	-1.22901	-0.61071
Ikot Akpa									
Edem	-0.79174	-1.05211	0.79178	-0.44717	0.1475	-1.35711	0.78564	-0.77017	-0.08021
Ikot Udo-									
Obong	-0.85547	-1.04122	0.99485	-0.28591	0.17726	-0.9648	0.90877	-0.40178	0.15369
Nto Obio	-0.94499	1.07833	0.60767	-0.15742	-0.29539	0.54389	0.6319	-0.39682	2.36804
Ikot Akpapan	-0.85935	-0.88298	0.54525	-1.10843	-0.56914	0.78383	0.2324	-0.78036	-0.97377
Ndot	-0.8212	-0.23291	-1.25596	-0.98709	0.38844	0.59237	0.20782	-1.37011	-0.59391
Ikot Abiat	-0.77834	1.14581	0.16566	0.00661	-0.70164	0.52284	0.80652	1.08817	-0.44794

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Nto Nsek	-0.92075	0.9683	0.22448	0.24565	-0.89211	1.06061	1.0771	1.22513	-0.37147
Ikot Akpan									
Essang	-0.75149	1.37122	0.52586	-0.28804	-0.54589	0.02643	0.40179	-0.57017	2.27599
Ikot Ntuen	-0.16766	-0.47314	0.83088	1.94019	0.20957	-1.71942	0.0114	-0.9478	-0.21771
Iboho	-0.78609	1.32561	0.15631	-0.3815	-1.17144	0.91247	0.53734	-1.31305	-0.92835
Mkpatak	-0.75205	-0.18112	-1.44958	-1.11346	-0.02388	-1.87427	0.42828	0.4353	-0.38288
Abat	1.10496	-0.5054	0.45819	-0.26206	-0.62432	-1.26257	0.698	0.81409	-0.23816
Ikot Onwon	-0.32155	-0.04167	-1.11127	-0.44393	0.35482	0.19751	-2.47342	0.89286	2.37301
Ikot Nya	-0.75307	1.33089	0.23065	-0.98123	0.11844	0.32506	0.08806	-0.92821	-0.90417
Urue Ita	2.83531	-0.38057	1.02893	-0.84657	-0.23391	-0.10763	0.01286	0.96245	-0.37052
Esuk Inwang									
Ekeya	-0.97425	-0.42433	-1.12998	-0.96442	0.32434	0.12097	0.27404	-0.0213	2.27449
Ebighi Anwa	-0.51839	-1.0207	0.70023	1.59237	0.43113	0.04381	-0.24128	-1.08714	1.84095
Eyo Nko	0.01414	-0.38268	0.94147	0.54842	-0.4852	-1.18208	-1.81579	-0.39256	0.24522
Nda	-0.15159	-0.00317	-1.54447	0.15938	-0.92097	-1.26433	-1.77943	0.11946	-0.29986
Obot Ndom	-0.62997	-0.56442	0.71664	-0.99956	-0.41513	-1.82514	0.36092	0.57949	-0.27819
Ikot Abia	-0.97374	-1.18336	0.67568	-1.57636	0.767	-0.35598	-0.09069	0.31704	1.87728
Uda	0.99971	0.0074	-1.31304	-0.1944	0.45093	1.07177	0.45617	-1.13898	-0.30518
Asak Ikang	-0.09821	-0.49628	0.85379	-0.19221	0.21941	-1.43359	-2.1584	0.82358	0.01539
Iyesin	0.00708	1.739	0.34702	0.63507	-0.85233	-1.32292	-1.78621	0.05079	-0.05891
Ibete	1.0177	-0.66676	0.37318	-0.46328	-0.67496	0.02607	0.29255	0.02726	1.92985
Ikot Inyang	-0.20032	0.29316	-1.37492	-0.8775	-0.16215	0.66507	-2.69521	0.85297	-0.76212
Mkpanak	-0.76548	-1.30001	-0.00428	-1.11804	-0.28473	-0.1457	0.05521	-0.00645	-0.83842
Esuk Mbiam	-0.84886	1.90182	1.94702	-0.33983	1.81664	1.89075	0.23095	1.41039	1.07432
Mbiaso	1.57988	1.5335	0.60627	-0.31655	-0.38404	-0.2177	-2.49776	0.48953	-0.6134
Ikot Inuen	-0.27326	-0.11531	-1.36613	-0.01808	-0.13063	1.10771	-2.14184	-1.19533	-0.58017
Obianga	2.74475	-0.78348	1.24679	-0.34423	0.88828	0.13693	0.29509	-0.56232	0.00643
Ntak Ibesit	1.06441	1.50674	-0.19073	-0.40005	-0.83885	-0.2865	0.24424	0.27903	1.67255
Ikot Osudu	0.87825	-0.26503	-1.76088	-0.56143	-0.37109	0.08195	0.38547	0.0807	1.85383
Ikot Akpa									
Idiang	1.01923	-0.26047	-1.71108	0.31061	-0.51369	-1.10679	1.13707	-0.93284	-0.20804
Atan Obom	0.96224	1.27599	-0.14477	-0.6169	0.04308	-0.32712	0.16331	0.35182	1.70369
Ikot Ukpang									
Ekwere	0.89387	-0.41877	-2.01653	0.18576	-0.9408	0.84026	1.01643	1.21116	-0.68089
Atan Ukwuk	1.11549	-0.53946	0.72256	-0.36913	0.71134	0.72328	0.21296	-1.31639	-0.36218
Akani Obio									
Uruan	2.78373	-0.82022	0.87442	-0.61183	0.45075	-0.26593	0.17784	-0.71226	-0.45089
Ikot Akpaidem	2.65343	-0.20774	-1.1311	-0.71391	0.35637	0.01125	0.26456	0.14907	-0.41564
Afaha Obo	0.21705	1.73638	-0.06249	0.41469	4.86949	-0.01888	0.30243	-1.31551	-0.71773
Ubodung	-0.11054	-0.66396	-2.15107	0.10177	5.97977	-0.40038	0.6034	0.81371	-0.73093
Eyo Eyekip	0.99622	-0.7389	0.62377	-0.19741	0.32783	1.09076	0.45428	-1.37186	-0.46872
Offot	1.48343	-0.86178	1.08709	-0.28192	0.01481	0.09559	-2.34939	-0.39416	-0.41649
Eyo Nsek	0.84429	-0.5298	-2.1552	0.12291	-1.09662	0.8567	1.05281	1.2207	-0.8541
Ekpene Obo	-0.40729	-0.41127	-1.52359	0.04843	-0.22625	1.33489	-1.95429	-1.42244	-0.75645
Uquo Iso									
Edoho	0.94252	-0.57428	1.01936	0.56616	-0.26248	1.66209	1.00027	2.54284	0.42083
Ine Ukpana	-0.45112	-0.39193	-1.20954	0.04809	0.05722	0.6633	-2.04511	-0.05544	2.33844
Ntak Inyang	-0.17536	-0.68831	0.89213	0.07011	0.33106	-1.16056	-1.94852	0.35202	0.10361
Akpata	2.78592	-0.53808	0.91326	-0.38676	-0.90806	0.24945	0.37057	0.21873	-0.43645
Ibesit									
Okpokoro	0.99846	-0.26445	-1.83206	-0.10206	-0.00047	0.38574	0.6823	1.30909	-0.48328
Itung	0.84241	-0.32546	-1.48891	0.46982	-0.98574	0.93649	1.00237	-1.00369	2.3145
Eteben	-0.1291	0.30056	-1.20282	2.27365	-0.40169	-1.59205	0.21984	-1.22199	-0.11702
Ntak Obio									
Akpa	1.09368	-0.61598	0.42987	-0.2345	-0.23028	0.82377	0.39717	-1.57901	-0.68954

Source: Researchers' statistical analysis (2025)

However, the implication of the nine (9) extracted components was renamed and explained using the rotated component matrix as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Rotated component matrix on rural participation approach

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Interactive	.836	-.007	-.112	-.095	-.098	.111	.648	.018	.137
Partnership	.695	-.085	.791	-.144	.008	-.004	-.154	.006	-.111
Empowerment	-.659	.062	.177	-.552	-.090	.641	.673	.676	-.060
Material donation	-.080	.933	.218	-.030	.016	.079	.087	.765	.015
Technical Assistance	.760	-.717	.653	.017	-.032	-.078	-.020	-.003	-.083
Counterpart Funding	-.003	-.144	-.937	.012	.019	.007	-.065	-.031	.077
Self-Mobilization	-.144	-.018	.016	.851	-.023	-.106	.021	-.010	-.053
Idea	-.049	-.051	.153	-.050	.817	.137	.533	.017	.084
Consultation	.008	.800	-.166	.039	.813	-.031	.068	-.038	-.109
Manipulative Money	-.130	-.093	.058	.123	-.128	-.870	.045	-.054	-.092
Functional	-.061	-.053	.841	.360	-.268	.534	.367	-.020	.147
Management	.000	-.088	-.050	.001	-.061	.015	-.929	.037	.008
Instrumental	.520	.508	.071	-.169	-.047	-.052	-.149	.765	-.007
Policy	-.131	.620	-.083	.733	.098	.341	.209	.676	-.231
Developmental	-.167	.512	.035	.851	.079	.475	-.107	-.515	-.395
Labour	-.021	.029	-.124	-.071	-.047	.075	-.022	-.059	.928
	.930	.503	.722	.283	.165	.297	.181	-.025	.593

Source: Researchers' statistical analysis (2025)

Key:

1. Organization of people factor
2. Material provision/ labour motivation factor
3. Technical assistance factor
4. Self-motivated factor
5. Individual initiative factor
6. Financial motivation factor
7. Monetary empowerment factor
8. Material availability factor
9. Labour interaction factor

However, the relationship was investigated using a multiple regression analysis. A multiple regression analysis of the nine (9) extracted components from 17 original variables on rural participation approaches indicators were regressed with the rural water supply options (each of the

4 Y-dependent variables). This was with a view to define the level of association of the two sets of variables as well as their causal relationships. For the Y1 variable (rain water supply options), a multiple correlation coefficient of $R = 0.570$ was obtained indicating that about 32.5% ($r^2=.325$) of this variable is impacted by the nine (9) extracted factor scores (X- variables). The square of the multiple correlations co-efficient R indicates the degree of predictability of the value of Y with all the X- variables taken together as input data using simultaneous or standardized multiple regression analysis. Using the specific contributions of each of the individual factors, X3 (Technical Assistance factor) contributed the highest in predicting the approaches of rural participation (0.961) while X8 (Labour Interaction factor) contributed the least (0.484) in the explanation of the approaches of rural participation in rural supply options.

However, rural participation approaches do significantly influence the rural water supply options in the study area going by the significant p- value of .000 which is less than .05 established for accepting the null hypothesis (see Table 4). Thus, the substantive hypotheses is rejected while the null hypotheses are accepted.

Y1 – Rain Water

Y2 – Stream

Y3 – Open Well

Y4 - Borehole

Table 4: Summarized result of multiple regression analysis

Parameters	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4
Multiple R	.570	.576	.483	.489
R Square	.325	.332	.234	.240
Adjusted R ²	.251	.259	.149	.156
Standard Error	2.159	2.207	1.914	2.846
F Change	4.396	4.534	2.776	2.871
Sig F	.000	.000	.000	.000
Durbin-Watson	1.952	1.826	2.078	1.776

Source: Researchers analysis result (2025).

Hypothesis Two

Ho: Socio – economic factors do not significantly influence the level of participation in rural water supply options in the study area. To analysed the hypothesis, factor analysis was used to reduce

the original 24 Socio – economic variables to Six (6) extracted component variables with their factor loadings as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Six extracted component factor scores on socio – economic variables

Community	1	2	3	4	5	6
Ikot Akpaya	0.25512	-0.42631	0.47399	0.13389	-0.75548	-0.0375
Ikot Umiang Ede	-0.68534	0.80594	-1.2813	1.08655	0.22398	-0.01218
Akpasak Efa	0.24608	1.63344	0.15777	-0.01965	-0.24234	-0.65828
Ikot Ananga	-0.46473	-0.10794	-0.93209	-0.23207	-0.29759	0.40168
Atan Aya	-0.52027	0.21553	-0.54416	-1.07414	-0.3567	-0.51915
Afaha Nsai	-0.00536	-1.59043	1.02029	0.45271	-0.10057	1.49538
Ikot Idem	0.13799	-0.99808	0.04127	-0.83058	0.23061	0.05777
Ikot Ada Idem	0.52158	0.1815	1.10716	-0.39422	0.55413	-0.14338
Usuk Aka	0.46009	0.17864	-0.13096	-0.97749	-0.33893	0.50486
Odiok Itam	-0.60523	1.64077	-0.05943	-0.46692	0.18512	-0.5524
Ikot Antuen	0.24262	-1.68565	0.55705	-0.10288	0.45028	0.08209
Ikot Offiong	1.0938	0.00881	0.24211	-0.65199	-0.10928	2.05952
Ndiya Etuk	0.78791	-0.46047	-1.09053	-0.36475	0.45534	0.97843
Itak Ikot Akpan Edem	-1.68303	0.564	0.58322	-0.02399	-0.00612	2.01569
Ikot Onwong	-1.49209	-0.86265	-1.48701	1.68794	1.3175	1.81685
Ekpen Obom Nkuoro	-0.87755	-0.56046	0.42443	-0.32034	-0.0148	-0.04466
Ikot Ette	0.08889	-0.97706	-1.25945	-1.04763	0.42923	1.80161
Etok Iton	-0.34891	-1.25602	-0.82716	0.75005	-0.18297	0.06074
Utu Edem Usuk	2.68573	-0.18198	1.21043	-1.48312	-0.88415	0.46291
Ndot Nkpe	0.44015	-0.4049	0.66744	-0.38345	-0.3005	0.95722
Ibam Edet	-1.45677	0.31867	0.53047	1.51469	-1.12624	-0.06619
Ikot Ukap	-0.919	0.06432	-0.98597	1.45941	-0.69395	-0.63022
Edem Idim	-0.55974	0.07622	-1.03409	-0.60886	0.05033	-0.47821
Idikpa Nsit	-0.46732	-0.16803	-0.50628	0.12568	-0.70405	0.69244
Ikot Uyo	0.22239	-0.18246	-0.63	-0.67068	-0.94362	-0.42398
Ikot Okpudo	-0.57796	-0.29083	0.98363	-0.75156	2.78237	0.03077
Minya Ntak	0.75193	-0.42073	0.87355	0.36324	0.67304	0.55798
Minya	-1.49808	1.28438	1.3081	-0.24764	1.0157	-0.57045
Ikot Etefia	-1.45049	-0.96003	0.9655	1.63982	0.76871	-0.99125
Ikot Annung	-0.06591	0.27182	-1.39471	1.24869	-1.92601	-0.92633
Ikot Obio Odongo	-0.46504	-0.68564	1.11625	0.58434	0.64453	3.04036
Ikot Akpasia	-0.27542	-0.45473	0.42607	-0.75223	-0.99139	0.06508
Ekpene Ukpa	1.94725	-0.36275	2.51995	0.66722	0.94501	-1.832
Odio	-0.43987	0.13228	0.3919	1.02757	0.93963	-1.19607
Esit Urua	0.50608	-0.34111	1.1659	1.6503	1.17709	-0.11186
Ikot Abia	1.05699	-0.25004	-0.60818	0.54774	1.66302	-0.42011
Nditia	0.08998	-0.55474	-0.83024	-0.76535	-0.40115	-0.32715
Afaha Esang	2.36766	-0.69313	-0.43541	-1.0796	0.87281	0.15488
Ikot Obioko	0.16686	0.66601	-0.91834	1.56484	-1.65305	-0.7294
Ikwek	-0.69046	-0.72651	0.27465	1.81925	0.41922	-0.26547
Ikot Akpa Edem	0.13286	-0.48142	-0.58177	-0.34418	-0.08561	-0.68204
Ikot Udo-Obong	0.87529	-1.30814	-0.98915	2.50225	2.06338	-1.64886
Nto Obio	0.5429	0.73409	1.12268	-0.59814	0.16247	-1.13094
Ikot Akpapan	0.76365	-0.71382	-0.0598	-1.03405	-0.72699	-0.17864
Ndot	0.1656	-0.26865	-1.46543	-0.25183	-0.41565	0.13707
Ikot Abiat	0.68964	0.50622	-0.42397	-0.74345	-1.89842	-0.60107
Nto Nsek	0.5987	0.323	0.99947	-0.78984	0.22311	-0.439
Ikot Akpan Essang	0.16021	-0.56175	-0.10239	-0.08011	-0.16122	-0.63057

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Ikot Ntuen	-0.2749	0.39047	-1.26105	0.55212	-0.86607	-0.64443
Iboho	0.03937	0.22322	-1.2636	-0.67596	-0.45923	-0.26095
Mkpatak	-0.79219	-0.63168	0.14059	-0.91727	1.05489	-0.25063
Abat	0.21448	-0.58091	2.02571	-0.02669	-0.54881	0.69802
Ikot Onwon	0.61247	0.51467	1.62098	-0.13053	-2.49584	0.1887
Ikot Nya	-1.51497	0.00591	0.19462	-0.52352	0.50843	-0.36504
Urue Ita	0.31646	0.30418	-0.01175	0.17745	-0.05995	1.45551
Esuk Inwang Ekeya	-0.9967	0.58661	0.87369	0.88167	-1.36557	1.96421
Ebighi Anwa	-0.73944	0.24932	0.76853	-0.00775	-1.08537	-0.02451
Eyo Nko	-1.05579	-0.0481	0.56578	-1.20691	0.11052	1.21467
Nda	-0.37862	-0.20389	-1.26929	-0.60321	0.66328	-0.60592
Obot Ndom	-0.54671	0.72035	-1.38216	0.30612	-1.01728	0.51501
Ikot Abia	-0.94353	0.4443	1.07615	-1.25045	-0.29678	0.04621
Uda	1.4871	0.43789	-1.60784	-0.42574	1.7094	-0.89217
Asak Ikgang	0.06491	0.14702	-0.23625	-1.57816	2.00552	0.81264
Iyesin	0.38024	-1.27999	-0.37084	-0.70604	0.97833	-0.33799
Ibete	-0.4159	-0.29454	0.13072	0.87892	-1.22847	-0.52939
Ikot Inyang	1.1061	-0.22115	-1.28673	-0.73808	0.37183	2.693
Mkpanak	2.00673	5.29866	1.22773	3.08835	0.8569	2.77977
Esuk Mbiam	0.36028	-0.18559	-0.39536	-1.52801	-0.89077	0.24949
Mbiaso	-0.90741	0.07363	-0.06867	0.32201	-0.24032	-0.69206
Ikot Inuen	-0.73002	1.20836	0.31018	0.69866	-0.13855	-0.3211
Obianga	-0.32734	-0.8116	-0.18008	-0.19112	0.39432	-0.31963
Ntak Ibesit	-0.72601	-0.70069	0.90727	2.00955	-1.703	-0.35412
Ikot Osudu	-0.74855	0.51372	0.56821	-1.03917	-0.49455	-0.71476
Ikot Akpa Idiang	-1.62762	-1.92645	1.31281	2.32973	0.95751	-0.47854
Atan Obom	0.77884	0.41982	-1.465	0.07859	-1.03253	-0.98261
Ikot Ukpong Ekwere	0.26906	-0.44522	-1.14972	0.16901	0.49045	1.68769
Atan Ukwuk	-0.84453	-0.01092	-0.0581	-0.6715	-0.4727	-0.44554
Akani Obio Uruan	-0.22975	-0.53621	0.61866	-0.07574	0.74956	2.01692
Ikot Akpaidem	1.34683	0.2655	-1.52635	1.16509	-0.45071	0.43183
Afaha Obo	-2.26187	3.50495	-0.38072	-1.62897	3.081	-1.50356
Ubodung	0.56656	-1.41751	0.51066	0.31695	2.09085	-1.06623
Eyo Eyekip	0.04699	-1.10895	-0.50157	-0.253	-0.25115	-0.52981
Offot	0.08436	-0.37342	-0.74468	0.68055	-0.86583	-0.24912
Eyo Nsek	-0.98441	1.37094	-0.49577	-0.86861	-0.03619	-1.20079
Ekpene Obo	3.9491	1.13389	1.07846	0.91481	0.67148	-1.62324
Uquo Iso Edoho	1.72301	0.18873	-1.3341	-0.14488	-0.29043	-0.05507
Ine Ukpana	0.86943	-1.05318	0.77725	1.06892	-1.17997	-0.82665
Ntak Inyang	-0.33156	1.90093	-0.99243	0.22275	-0.39303	-0.58349
Akpata	0.46062	-0.18617	-1.39728	0.19578	0.15546	-0.79761
Ibesit Okpokoro	0.05545	0.33878	3.04883	-1.55303	-1.08545	-1.09117
Itung	-0.20695	-0.37307	0.82907	-1.25675	-1.11983	-0.45829
Eteben	-1.25993	0.20733	1.08777	-1.28006	-0.32206	-0.18424
Ntak Obio Akpa	-0.34306	1.27087	-0.87979	-0.51136	0.61082	0.50904

Source: Researchers' Statistical Analysis (2025)

However, the six (6) extracted components was renamed and the rotated component matrix is used to explain the implications of the renamed components as it implies to this study as seen in Table 6.

Table 6: Rotated component matrix for socio – economic factor

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
Secondary. School	.795	.101	.181	.038	-.005	.211
Trading	.752	.376	.166	-.060	.019	-.104
Business	.751	.047	.290	.108	.160	-.078
Single	.745	.231	-.049	.395	.287	.112
Age: 19 -37yrs	.659	.184	.230	.304	.253	.116
Age: < 18yrs	.557	.249	-.133	.412	.241	.016
Male	.553	.475	.331	.353	.256	.117
Income: ₦36-72	.515	.428	.647	.042	-.006	.412
Female	.494	.429	.592	.273	.190	.148
Age: >57 yrs	.133	.800	.030	.056	.203	.068
Devoiced	.212	.654	.267	.056	-.020	.211
Widowed	.192	.649	.184	.087	-.009	.369
Income: ₦72-108	.299	.624	.072	.535	-.073	-.215
Primary Education	.345	.567	.689	.155	.086	-.137
Farming	-.065	.566	.533	.035	.550	.026
No formal Edu.	.267	.543	.153	.278	.444	.201
Age: 38-56	.193	.248	.836	.182	.004	.171
Married	.286	.206	.744	.296	.278	-.107
Public Service	.167	.253	.186	.807	-.076	.219
Post Education	.017	-.092	.204	.658	.518	.117
Poly/Uni. Education	.389	.290	.349	.513	.060	.171
Income level > ₦ 144	.340	-.003	.291	.409	.507	-.181
Income level ₦ 108 - 144	.358	.110	.041	.106	.768	.125
Clergy	.062	.201	.029	.182	.137	.874

Source: Researchers’ Statistical Analysis (2025)

Key:

- | | |
|----|---|
| 1. | Post-secondary youth/informal occupation |
| 2. | Non-formally educated and married youth |
| 3. | Lowly educated and married youth |
| 4. | Highly educated and employed youth |
| 5. | Highly educated and high-income professionals |
| 6. | Middle income unmarried clergy |

A multiple correlation/regression analysis of the six (6) extracted components from 24 original variables on socio – economic indicators were regressed with the rural water supply options. This was with a view to define the level of association of the two sets of variables as well as their causal relationships. For the Y1 variable (rain water supply options), a multiple correlation coefficient of $R = 0.591$ was obtained indicating that about 34.9% ($r^2=.349$) of this variable is impacted by the six (6) extracted factor scores (X- variables). The square of the multiple correlations coefficient R indicates the degree of predictability of the value of Y with all the X- variables taken together as input data using simultaneous or standardized multiple regression analysis. Using the specific contributions of each of the individual factors, X2 (formally educated and married youth factor) contributed the highest in predicting the socio – economic factor contributions of (0.531) while X6 (religious income factor) contributed the least (-. 045) in the explanation of the socio – economic factors influence to rural water supply options in the study area. Therefore, the null hypothesis in this case is rejected as the overall result shows that the socio – economic factors do significantly influence the rural water supply options in rural Akwa Ibom State going by the

significant p- value of .000 which is less than .05 established for accepting the null hypothesis (see Table 7.).

Table 7: Summarized result of multiple regression analysis

Parameters	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4
Multiple R	.591	.723	.604	.636
R Square	.349	.523	.365	.404
Adjusted R ²	.304	.490	.320	.362
Standard Error	2.074	1.823	1.702	2.464
F	7.688	15.10	8.228	9.711
Sig F	.000	.000	.000	.000
Durbin-Watson	1.574	1.662	2.053	1.725

Source: Researchers analysis result (2025)

4. Conclusion/ Recommendations

Nigeria is one of the developing countries of the world that are in a very poor state of the provision of social amenities especially rural water supply despite several policies and programme by successive administrations. Studies have differently confirmed that majority of rural communities in Nigeria lack access to the improved water supply. Often times, they rely on free water supply sources such as streams and unprotected wells for their water needs which are susceptible to waterborne disease. This is a true reflection in the study area as the majority of the rural dwellers indicated that their source of water supply was from borehole but regrettably these sources were not functioning as the majority of the rural dwellers still source their water needs from streams and unprotected wells.

Methods of rural participation approach in the provision of rural water supply to reduce the burden of access to the improved water supply was analysed and concluded that; labour interaction factor participation was low. This was due to several factors amongst which was the health and educational level of the rural dwellers thereby limiting their participation in rural supply projects in the study area. However, religious income factor contributed the least in explaining the socio - economic factors influencing rural water supply in the study area. Thus, the study recommends that the social economic status of the rural dwellers should be strengthened to enable them effectively participates in rural water supply projects while the technical assistant approach should be sustained

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